

One Health EJP WP4 Thematic Integrative Meeting

DATA SHARING ACROSS DISCIPLINES

22 February 2022: 9.30-12.00 CET via Teams

We would like to invite you to this requested digital seminar "Data sharing across disciplines".

Two legal advisors and one OHEJP project participant will give their views on the legal framework, challenges and solutions when it comes to sharing data in for example disease outbreaks, surveillance and research projects.

The aim of the Thematic Integrative Meetings (TIMs) is to facilitate integration across the OHEJP domains, within themes. We consider this TIM to be of interest for e.g. OHEJP project participants, management staff at the partner institutes and those who will take part in the upcoming OHEJP exercise "SimEx". Feel free to distribute the invitation to those who might be interested.

PROGRAMME

- 9.30-9.40** **Welcome**
Karin Artursson, SVA, Sweden
- 9.40-10.10** **General challenges regarding data sharing – building blocks that need to be in place**
Kristina Andersson, RISE, Sweden
- 10.10-10.40** **Challenges and solution for sharing data and models in Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessments**
Laurent Guillier (JIP CARE), ANSES, France
- 10.40-11.00** **Break**
- 11.00-12.00** **Sharing data: How to do it in real-life situations**
Serena Faccio, DTU, Denmark
Interactive session targeting actual situations

REGISTRATION

If you would like to attend, please let us know by 15 February 2022, by sending us an e-mail to: OHEJP@sva.se with your full name and affiliation.

We might need to restrict the number of participants. In this case a first come, first served basis is applied.

A link to the meeting will be sent out a couple of days before the meeting.

The meeting will be recorded and made available upon request. If you register for the meeting you agree to the recording.

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IMAGE: PXHERE